

Issues of perfect human education in the scientific and pedagogical views of Abu Rayhan Beruni

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ANNOTATION

Beruni shows that nobility is one of the qualities that lead a person to perfection. Goodness is the essence of nobility. By this, a scientist means treating a person as a person. Most importantly, the thinker expresses important ideas about human development, labor and labor education. It is divided into types depending on the work of each craftsman. As hard work, he brings the labor of builders, coal miners, artisans, and scientists.

IMPORTANT CONCEPTS:

correctness, justice, restraint, envy, stinginess, wisdom, shame, neatness, refined taste, chastity, grace, Heredity. 2. Environment. 3. Education.

According to Beruni, morality should be the most basic quality of a person. This quality does not develop suddenly. It is formed in the process of human interaction, social environment - development of society. Beruni also defines moral education based on the requirements of the Muslim religion. He says that morality is manifested and formed as a result of the struggle between good and evil. Goodness and badness are used as criteria for determining human behavior.

He includes good qualities such as correctness, justice, self-control, honesty, humility, grace, steadfastness, prudence, generosity, sweetness, fairness in leadership, and entrepreneurship. Bad vices include envy, avarice, unhealthy competition, self-interest, careerism, etc. Beruni uses pride in the sense of good manners and says in "Memorials": "Pride is in fact to go ahead in good manners and high deeds, to acquire knowledge and wisdom, and to be cleansed of existing impurities as much as possible. Whoever has these qualities, the judgment will be in his favor, and whoever lacks them, the judgment will be against him." Therefore, Beruni divides all moral qualities in the spiritual image of a person into two types, such as good and bad. Just as this is a "red thread" in the development of pedagogical thought created by humanity, moral

concepts are also important aspects of moral perfection in Beruni according to this tradition.

External generosity (mutual help, cooperation to benefit each other), benevolence (being kind to people, honesty and truthfulness, making a living with one's own work, etc.) are qualities that show the moral maturity of a person knows that

The problem of moral maturity of a person has been a central issue in the entire educational system. Abu Rayhan Beruni condemns such defects as avarice, lying, hypocrisy, conceit, and arrogance, which prevent good wishes, and considers the desire for wealth and greed, anger and ignorance to be the worst enemies of man. Another of the moral feelings put forward by the thinker is justice. He says that in order to establish justice in the society, to rid it of evils, it is necessary to have a wise and just ruler. Beruni also paid great attention to the issues of daily life. Every morally sound person can make his lifestyle harmonious and beautiful. It is considered the basis of harmony, beauty and sophistication. He says that the most important external human qualities are freedom and education, and the closest thing to a person is his nature and soul. Therefore, it shows that it is necessary for a person to do what is pleasing to his nature. In this, he demanded the harmony of the inner world of a person with his external beauty, beauty in his lifestyle. It is emphasized that everything should be beautiful, starting from the clothes a person wears, his behavior in his daily life, his words, his heart, and the work he does. The composition of modesty, neatness, elegant taste, chastity, grace, sweetness in every person makes life more beautiful.

The opinions of the scientist about the rules of conduct specific to human life are pedagogically important. He says that a person can achieve true perfection only if he is beautiful both inside and outside. He equates freedom and sophistication with nobility. A person always insists that it is necessary to follow them. He says that it is necessary for a person to be able to manage himself, to have the strength and will to develop the qualities necessary for every mature person. In the work "Minerology" he expresses this idea as follows. "A person is able to control his passions, change them, while training his soul and body, he is able to turn negative aspects into praiseworthy things and gradually eliminate vices using the methods shown in the books on morality."

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human development, labor and labor education. It is divided into types depending on the work of each craftsman. As hard work, he brings the labor of builders, coal miners, artisans, and scientists. He especially calls on people of science to pay special attention to the work of scientists, to be well-wishers. he says that it is necessary to talk about farmers and encourage their work. He especially reminds that kings should take care of such workers. Because they claim that these working people are the basis of their rule.

The scientist also thinks about methods and ways of teaching children to work. For example, he says that children should be taught to work from an early age. According to the traditions of that period, inheritance is very important in labor education. E. Torakulov and S. Rahimov explained this very well in their treatise "Abu Rayhan Beruni about spirituality and education". Beruni's work "Mineralogy" contains valuable ideas not only about precious metals and stones, but also about crafts, the process of training apprentices, and the methods of teaching crafts by masters. In this case, the current pedagogy, in the language of science, uses the personal sample method, and the fact that the work process is carried out both theoretically and practically in the workshop itself is of great importance for the students to become qualified masters. That is why Khorasan and Movarounnahr made a name for themselves in the world market in metallurgy, mining, weaving, jewelry making, paper and glass production and other fields at that time.

This kind of individual teaching of handicrafts helped to develop qualified professionals, led them to work honestly and conscientiously, which was an important step in the development of a person. After all, since ancient times, every mature person, whether he is a king or an ordinary citizen, has been considered necessary to know one or more types of trade. Accordingly, both nobles, beggars, wealthy property owners, and ordinary citizens paid attention to the fact that their children should be educated as well as skilled, and everyone obeyed this unwritten law. followed. Because, since the emergence of individual society, people have been forced to make a living by their work and craft, and this has been accepted as a requirement of life. That's why Beruni says that in order for a person to mature in all aspects, he should be knowledgeable as well as hardworking and skilled. Beruni emphasizes that three things are important in human maturity. The pedagogy of the present era is also a recognition of heredity, environment, and upbringing. In a certain period, scientists denied the influence of heredity and environment on human development and recognized only education. But Beruni, like his contemporaries - the great thinkers Farabi and Ibn Sina - considers all three important in human perfection.

That is, he emphasizes that although science, enlightenment, art and practice play a major role in the development of a person, genealogy, social environment and the laws of social life are also of great importance. According to Abu Rayhan Beruni, the most important factors of human maturity are knowledge and high morals. Beruni created a unique school in educational theory with his views on scientific knowledge and educational methods.

In the education of young people, concepts of moral work education, refinement education, family education, human personal hygiene, friendship and cooperation between peoples are of great importance. The scientist put forward goodness, correctness, justice, humility, generosity, nobility, friendship and cooperation, hard work and skill acquisition, purity, striving for beauty as signs of morality. He explained all this in connection with the socio-philosophical thoughts in his works. As can be seen from the above, Beruni's thoughts on the formation of a perfect person are not only for his time, but also of great importance for the improvement of modern education. After all, he proved that he has the qualities of a truly perfect person, with his life and creative work, he left a great spiritual legacy for future generations. Beruni became famous as one of the encyclopedic scholars of the "Eastern Renaissance" period. The famous American historian J. Sarton called the first half of the 11th century Beruni's period in the history of world science. He is also considered to be the first world wise man of his time. Beruni's creation of more than 150 major scientific works, covering both natural and social sciences, also confirms the validity of this opinion. Beruni considers man to be the highest perfection of nature. He divides all the moral qualities of the spiritual image of a person into two types, such as good and bad. According to Beruni's teachings, three things play an important role in human development:

1. Heredity.
2. Environment.
3. Education.

Beruni's thoughts on the ways and methods of acquiring scientific knowledge are also relevant for the current era. He teaches the student:

- not to bore the student;
- not to teach the same thing or the same subject in education;
- integrity, consistency;

- suggests the need to pay attention to interesting, mainly visual presentation of new topics and so on.

3. Abu Rayhan Beruni's academic activity at Mamun Academy.

Abu-Rayhan Muhammad ibn Ahmad al-Biruni is one of the greatest scholars of the Middle Ages. He mastered all the sciences of his time - physics, mathematics and natural-historical sciences. Beruni was not only a scientist, he was one of the prominent political figures of Khorezm in his time. One of the famous scholars of Central Asia, Abdulkarim al-Sam'ani (died in 1165) wrote in his book "Kitab al-Ansab" ("The Book of Genealogies"): "The nisba Beruni refers to the outer part of Khorezm. A person who was born outside the city is called "so-and-so beruni". Astrologer Abu Rayhan is famous for such ratio. Beruni had a strong interest and ability in science from a young age. But we do not have complete information about who and where he received his primary education. He studied under the famous scholar of his time, Abu Nasr ibn Iraq. Abu Nasr ibn Iraq wrote several works on astronomy, geometry and mathematics, dedicating 12 of them to Beruni. He introduces Beruni to Euclid's geometry and Ptolemy's astronomical teaching. Abu Nasr Mansour ibn Iraq wrote in one of his scientific works that Beruni made important astronomical observations in the city of Kot in 384-385 (AD 994-995), despite being a very young scientist when he lived in Khorezm. He invents astronomical instruments for these observations. But he was only able to determine the farthest and highest ecliptic point and ecliptic without azimuth for a certain village located south of Khorezm on the left bank of Jayhun (Amu Darya). In 995-997, Beruni went to Ray because of a coup d'état in Khorezm, where he met Mahmud al-Khojandi.

Beruni comes from Rai to Jurjon after 1000 years. Yakut Hamavi left important information about Beruni's life in Jurjan. He tells that he got acquainted with all the manuscripts of the scientist. According to Yaqt, Qabus offered Vashmgir Beruni a ministerial position, but the scientist did not agree to it.

Khorezmshah Abu-l-Abbas called Ma'mun II ibn Ma'mun Beruni to his court and honored him as a scholar. We mentioned above that Beruni was a mudarris in Ma'mun's academy and a political adviser of Ma'mun ibn Ma'mun.

Although the great thinker of the Eastern Renaissance, encyclopedist Abu Rayhan Beruni, did not write a special work reflecting socio-political and legal views, in his works such as "Monuments from Ancient Nations", "India", "Mineralogy", "Geodesy" and tried to explain the emergence of society, state management policy, social justice, community activities, division of labor and money circulation, family and marriage relations from a political and legal point of view.

Touching on the issue of the emergence of man and society, Beruni says, "The earliest and most famous of the ancient histories is the beginning of humanity." While thinking about the emergence of individual society, Beruni comes to the conclusion that although there are differences between people, the internal structure of people is common to all. One of the concepts that Abu Rayhan focuses on is social justice. The thinker describes social justice in connection with the relationship to property, human value, exchange and trade, money circulation, politics and education, obedience to laws, governing the state based on fair laws.

He says that the worst form of immorality in society is violence and theft, he shows ways to punish and re-educate people of this category, which confirms that the scientist is a humane jurist: "As for theft - o Punishment is given depending on the amount of the stolen item. Sometimes it is severe and moderate punishment that serves as an example to the people, sometimes it is stopped by torture and compensation, sometimes it is made public.

Beruni corresponded with Ibn Sina during his stay in Urganch. Only 18 of their questions and answers have reached us. 10 of these questions and answers were given to Aristotelian philosophy, and 8 to physics.

These correspondences show how much Beruni was interested in natural philosophy and physics. In the questions and answers, the two scientists argue about space, the spread of heat, the expansion of bodies from heat and water during freezing, the return and refraction of light. From the contents of the questions and answers, it is known that Beruni contradicted the conclusions of Aristotle based on his own observation and experience, and Ibn Sina defended Aristotle.

By 1017-1018, a period of turmoil begins in Urganch. A state of Qarani will be established in Movarounnahr. In Khurasan and Afghanistan, the famous Mahmud Ĵznavi (998-1030) established his rule. According to the agreement concluded between the Karakhanids and Mahmud, Amudarya will be the border of their state, Khorezm will be dependent on Mahmud's state and will be conquered by Mahmud later. The occupation of Khorezm by Mahmud Ĵznavi will be very difficult for Beruni. Later, through the mediation of people close to Mahmud, disputes arose between Beruni and the sultan, and the scientist was able to lead a peaceful life again. Beruni's life spent in the Treasury in 1017-1048 was, on the one hand, difficult, but on the other hand, it was the most productive period for his scientific activity. A scientist who has lived in the country and is free from interference in state affairs spends all his free time on scientific research. It was here that he wrote the works "Famous People of

Khorezm" and "Taḥdīd nihiyot al-amokin li tashih masofat al-masokin" ("Determining the final boundaries of places to check the distance between residential areas").

One of Beruni's important works that has come down to us, the manuscript "Basic Concepts of the Art of Astrology" is kept at the Institute of Oriental Studies named after Abu Rayhan Beruni of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It was also written in the Treasury in 1029. The work has reached us in Persian and Arabic languages. In 1030, his greatest work, known as "India", was "Tahqiq mo li-l-Hind min maqula maqula fi-l-aql av marzula" Mahmud Ĵznavi died in the year when "Hindistan" was finished. He appointed his younger son Muhammad as his successor. But after a few months, his eldest son Mas'ud (1030-1041) overthrew his brother and took over the state. During Mas'ud's time, Beruni's condition improved considerably. Yaqut Hamavi writes that Mas'ud was interested in astronomy and paid special attention to scientific observations. Beruni helps Mas'ud learn Arabic well. Mas'ud also took the scientist under his protection and was rewarded with gifts and gifts.

Beruni writes in the preface to Mas'ud's Law: "he [Mas'ud] gave me the opportunity to serve knowledge with an open face for the rest of my life, because he showed me grace by dressing me in an ornamental dress." In the shadow of the eternal, he put the cover of peace over him and showered the clouds of blessings. At the same time, he kept me close to him, invited me to talk to him one after another, and received me well."

"Qanuni Mas'udi" is the largest astronomical work of Abu Rayhan Beruni. According to Yaqut Hamavi, this work was superior to all previously written works in the field of astronomy and mathematics. Famous scholars such as Ibn al-Qifti and Abu-l-Fida put Beruni's work first. "Qanuni Mas'udi" was written in 1037 after Beruni's "Tafhim" and "India". The scientific activity of Abu Rayhan Beruni has not lost its importance even today. Many of his works have come down to us.

Summary

In short, Abu Rayhan Beruni's natural-scientific and philosophical social views play an important role in the development of world science. Indeed, the wisdom of education is the power of perspective. When we say the power of perspective, it is necessary to understand the high level of human intelligence, the prosperity and bright horizons of the society and state in which these people live, and the prestige of the world. Undoubtedly, this greatness is achieved through education. That is why our ancestors attached great importance to education in the first place. Human spirituality and enlightenment, intelligence, high morals, etc. are products of education. Education is not something that is put in a mold or a frame. When we say education, it is not just taking someone to a special room and giving advice, but also explaining the

lessons of life and life in a comparative way during education and science. It is necessary to understand and know the habit of setting a personal example. These factors should be combined with each other.

A person can be educated mainly in two ways: through the direct influence of others, i.e. teaching, as well as through reading the thoughts, teachings and works of the wise; a person draws appropriate conclusions from his thinking, people's behavior, what he has done and is doing; can be trained through the most powerful means of thinking.

In each society, certain customs and rituals of people are formed. They also express certain ideas, views, moral norms. Due to the independence of our country, new traditions, ceremonies and customs were established. As they become history, they embody great events, unforgettable events in the life of our people.

It is of great importance to know and study the various traditions and rituals, customs, and the conditions of their origin, which have been living together with the people, considering that the thinker, traditions and holidays should serve to educate every person of an independent society in a comprehensive way. Because, although these are ethnographic data, they are closely related to the history and past of the people.

These spiritual assets are considered as one of the main factors in educating young people in the spirit of patriotism.

The customs and traditions presented in the works of Abu Rayhan Beruni are considered a powerful tool of national education, a factor of uniting the people into a single spiritual unity. Through ceremonies, the spiritual world of a certain nation is revealed in the historical ethnographic direction, and young people form boundless love for their homeland and their people.

The ancient traditions, ceremonies and holidays of the Uzbek people, various festivals and public events have been one of the most important means of educating the young generation in the spirit of high human perfection for centuries. This is the main factor that ensures the longevity of our traditions. Folk traditions are distinguished by their deep meaning, cheerfulness, calling people to goodness, solemnity, color, beauty and spiritual elevation. Meaningful and impressive ceremonies and traditions, as an integral part of the system of our national values, have always encouraged our people and enriched national culture and social life. The purposeful use of the rich pedagogical heritage left to us by our ancestors in educating young people in the spirit of patriotism, the appropriate application of the didactic process guarantees an effective result.

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